

ALIGNMENT OF CARBON NANOTUBES IN GLASS FIBER COMPOSITES USING AC ELECTRIC FIELD

Charles E. Bakis¹, Ambuj Sharma¹ and Kon-Well Wang²

¹Dept. of Engineering Science and Mechanics, 212 EES Building,
Pennsylvania State University, University Park, PA 16802 USA
Email: cbakis@psu.edu, ambuj923@gmail.com

²Dept. of Mechanical Engineering, 2236 G. G. Brown Laboratory, 2350 Hayward,
University of Michigan, Ann Arbor, MI 48109 USA
Email: kwwang@umich.edu

Keywords: Carbon nanotubes; Alignment; Electrical properties; Glass fiber composite

ABSTRACT

The ability to detect delamination damage in fiber reinforced composites by electrical means can be enhanced by reducing the through-thickness electrical resistivity in comparison with the normally higher in-plane resistivity. Conductive nanofillers such as carbon nanotubes (CNTs) offer the potential to tailor the conductivity of otherwise highly resistive composites, such as glass fiber reinforced polymers (GFRPs), on account of their small size and high aspect ratio. The current investigation aims to assess the efficacy of aligning CNTs in the through-thickness direction of unidirectional GFRP using an alternating electric field applied during the curing process, thus decreasing the through-thickness resistivity. For a fixed alignment field strength of 1,000 V/cm, it was found by experimentation that a 100 Hz alignment field provides slightly better electrical tailoring than a 1,000 Hz field. The through-thickness resistivity could be reduced by one or two orders of magnitude, resulting in a composite with in-plane and through-thickness resistivities of nearly the same order of magnitude. A finite element analysis showed that improved alignment results can be expected when the alignment electrodes are in direct contact with the composite rather than separated by a release film of low dielectric constant, although the presence of glass fibers causes significant disturbances in the orientation of the electric field within the composite in either case.

1 INTRODUCTION

Carbon nanotubes (CNTs) have been investigated as multifunctional filler materials for conventional glass and carbon fiber reinforced polymer composites since the early 2000s on account of their high thermal conductivity, electrical conductivity, elastic modulus, and strength. Given that the aspect ratio of CNTs is generally high—often in excess of 1,000—the properties that they impart to continuous fiber composite can depend strongly on their orientation. The current investigation explores the development of anisotropic conductivity in CNT-filled unidirectional glass fiber reinforced polymer (GFRP) composites caused by applying an alternating current (AC) electric field on the composite prior to cure.

CNTs suspended in liquid epoxy are polarized by an applied electric field and experience electrostatic torque due to the interaction of their charge and the applied field. Furthermore, the oriented and polarized CNTs experience attraction towards each other and can form a network of conductive chains between the electrodes due to a number of phenomena such as dielectrophoresis, electrorotation, and AC electroosmosis [1]. Once the composite is cured, the preferential orientation of the CNTs is locked into place, preserving the tailored resistivity or conductivity. A potential advantage of laminated composites with low resistivity through the thickness is for detecting delaminations using electrical measurements [2,3,4]. Only a few experimental investigations of the electrical tailoring of GFRP via electric field alignment of CNTs have been reported to date [5,6]. Wichmann et al. [5] showed that the through-thickness resistivity of bi-directionally reinforced GFRP could be decreased by a factor of 10 with the electrical alignment of double-wall CNTs at a concentration of 0.3% by weight in the resin (0.3 wt%). This through-thickness resistivity was about 300 times greater than the in-plane resistivity after

alignment. Domingues et al. [6] showed that the alignment of 0.1 wt% multi-wall CNTs in bi-directionally reinforced GFRP laminates could reduce the through-thickness resistivity by a factor of 5—attaining a value 4 times greater than the in-plane resistivity. From these investigations, it is known that initially high resistivity through the thickness is challenging to overcome with electrically aligned CNTs, and that additional research could shed light on factors facilitating improved electrical tailoring.

The current investigation adds to the experimental database of anisotropic electrical properties of unidirectional GFRP composites with unaligned and electrically aligned CNTs and presents finite element simulations of the electric field within the composite during the alignment process. Ultimately, the long-range interest in this line of work is to develop GFRP composites with through-the-thickness resistivity as low as possible in relation to the in-plane resistivity, which is a potentially useful characteristic for structural health monitoring purposes.

2 EXPERIMENTAL METHODS

Epon 862 epoxide and Curative W—a bisphenol F epoxide and aromatic diamine curing agent—comprised the matrix material system. Non-covalently functionalized multi-wall CNTs of 15-50 nm diameter, pre-dispersed by the vendor (Zyvex Performance Materials, Columbus, OH, USA) in Epon 862 at 2 wt%, were selected as the conductive filler. The non-covalent functionalization increases the electrical percolation threshold of the CNTs, thereby allowing high weight contents of CNTs to align and chain in the direction of electric field [7]. The as-received CNT/epoxide mixture was diluted with additional Epon 862 and curing agent to obtain a concentration of 0.5 wt% in the matrix material used for making GFRP composites. The CNTs were manually mixed in an appropriate amount of epoxide using a plastic stirrer for 5 minutes. The mixture was then sonicated for 30 min. using a 20-kHz ultrasonic horn set at power level of 270 W. During sonication, the mixture was continuously cooled to prevent excessive heating. Curative was added and manually mixed for 5 min. using a plastic stirrer. The resin mixture was then degassed for one hour in a vacuum oven set to 70°C.

Due to the difficulty in infusing dense glass fiber preforms without filtration of the CNTs, GFRP pre-impregnated sheets were wet wound on a flat mandrel using a computer controlled filament winder, a resin bath, and E-glass roving. The fiber volume content (V_f) of the wetted roving was set to either 45% or 55% by passing the fiber through a precision orifice at the exit of the resin bath. The fibers were wound using five forward and backward strokes of the carriage, resulting in a $[\pm 1]_5$ laminate that, for present purposes, is considered unidirectional. The prepreg sheets were degassed in a vacuum oven at 70°C for 30 min and cut into 2×6.5 cm pieces. Two 2×2 cm aluminum foil electrodes were placed onto these pieces of unidirectional prepreg for applying an electric field through the thickness during cure (Fig. 1). Curing was done with a slight through-thickness pressure applied to the composite using a pair of release-coated glass plates. The curing schedule consisted of gelling at 121°C for 1 h and post-curing at 177°C for 2.5 h. The electrical alignment field of 1,000 V/cm strength (peak-to-peak) was applied at frequencies of either 100 or 1,000 Hz during gelation. The values selected for the field strength and frequencies were based on previous experience aligning Z-MWCNTs in neat epoxy [7]. The field strength was substantially larger than that required for Z-MWCNTs in neat epoxy (100 V/cm) in Ref. [7] because of the expectation of substantial drag forces exerted on the CNTs by the densely packed glass fibers in the current investigation.

After cure, the alignment electrodes were peeled off, and the 1.5-mm-thick specimens were trimmed with a water-cooled diamond saw to the 2×2 cm region within the alignment electrodes, towel dried, and further dried for 3 hours on a hot plate at 60°C. A small amount of resin flowed out of the material during consolidation, although it was not measured and the actual fiber and void contents of the materials are unknown.

Figure 1: Schematic of setup used for aligning CNTs in GFRP composites.

DC resistance values were measured with a two-point probe in three orthogonal directions: (i) perpendicular to the fibers, parallel to the electrical alignment field (i.e., through-thickness); (ii) parallel to the fibers, perpendicular to the alignment field; and (iii) perpendicular to the fibers and the alignment field (Fig. 2). Since the resistances were anticipated to be in the millions of ohms, contact resistances were neglected. The two opposite surfaces were polished using a 600 grit abrasive paper and then coated with a conducting silver-filled acrylic paint to provide good electrical contact. Thin copper wires were then soldered to the conducting faces. From the measured resistance, the volume resistivity of the specimen, ρ_{DC} , was determined using the formula,

$$\rho_{DC} = RA/L \quad (1)$$

where R is the resistance of the specimen measured by dividing the applied voltage by the current, L is the length of the specimen between the electrical contacts, and A is the cross-sectional area of the specimen normal to the direction of current flow. One specimen was prepared for each of the three directions of resistance measurement for each of two alignment frequencies (plus no alignment) and each of two glass fiber volume fractions. Thus, 18 specimens were evaluated in total.

Figure 2: Schematic of specimens prepared for DC resistivity measurements.

3 FINITE ELEMENT ANALYSIS

Since CNTs align and chain in the direction of electric field, the ability to align CNTs in continuous fiber composites depends on the spatial distribution of electric field. The prediction of the electric field distribution in composites using analytical techniques is not straightforward, but it can be estimated using finite element analysis.

Hydrodynamic forces exerted by the liquid resin on CNT chains, which arise from AC electroosmosis and can have a large influence on CNT chain formation in neat epoxy [8], are not considered in this investigation. The reason for neglecting hydrodynamic forces is due to the large hydrodynamic resistance provided to the fluid flow by the closely spaced glass fibers. In addition, it is anticipated that the movement of individual CNTs will be restricted due to their proximity to continuous fibers. Nevertheless, the CNTs can still be expected to form chains because they do not have to translate large distances on account of their high concentration in the resin. An order-of-magnitude estimation of the

mean distance R' between randomly distributed CNTs can be obtained using an expression for the center-to-center spacing between aligned, hexagonally arranged cylinders of radius r ,

$$\ln\left(\frac{R'}{r}\right) = \frac{1}{2} \ln\left(\frac{2\pi}{\sqrt{3}V_f}\right) \quad (2)$$

where V_f is the volume fraction of CNTs in the matrix [9]. For a weight concentration of 0.5% in the matrix, the separation distance of the CNTs is of the order of 100 nm. Thus, given that the CNTs are actually randomly oriented rather than unidirectional, it can be expected that they need to translate less than 10 times their diameter to make contact with another CNT.

Due to the large difference in the sizes of CNTs (nm), glass fibers (μm), and the distance between the electrodes (mm) in the actual specimens evaluated, the entire region between the electrodes cannot be modeled within a practical limit of around 500,000 nodes in the finite element model. As a result, a sub-region was modeled with randomly-positioned glass fibers and homogeneous (effective) properties for the CNT-filled resin. The resistivity of generic glass fiber is 10^{16} $\Omega\text{-cm}$ and the measured resistivity of the Z-MWCNT/liquid resin mixture was approximately 10^{10} $\Omega\text{-cm}$. Thus, neither the fibers nor the matrix are considered conductors, although the matrix is much more conductive than the glass fiber. The models were solved assuming dielectric glass fibers embedded in a dielectric medium. Dielectric constants for CNT reinforced resin and glass fiber were assumed to be 100 [10] and 4.2 [11], respectively.

Based on the geometry of the electrodes and the unidirectional orientation of the glass fibers, the cross-section of the composite material can be modeled as a two-dimensional domain. The finite element software used in this investigation was COMSOL Multiphysics [11]. The Electrostatics Module available in COMSOL was used for solving the Laplace's equation for the electric potential in the region between the electrodes (Fig. 3). The problem was solved non-dimensionally. The domain is meshed with an unstructured triangular mesh, with refinement near the surface of the glass fibers. The mesh was generated using the automatic mesh generation feature available in the software. The boundary conditions for the models are shown in Fig. 3. The displacement current, given by the product of dielectric constant and the electric field, is assumed constant across the fiber/matrix interface. The finite element analysis was done prior to doing the experiments, using glass fiber volume contents of 40% and 50%. These constituent contents are slightly lower than the experimental estimates of 45% and 55%, which are themselves lower bounds due to consolidation. However, the finite element results are only intended to provide general trends to supplement the experimental observations.

In some composite manufacturing procedures, it may be necessary to use a release film between the composite and the electrodes. Therefore, the effects of a polytetrafluoroethylene (PTFE) release film on the distribution of electric field were also investigated using finite element analysis. The geometry and boundary conditions for this analysis are shown in Fig. 4. The release film is assumed to have a dielectric constant of 2 [11].

4 EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS

Figure 5 shows the DC electrical resistance measurements for the cured composites. The results clearly show that, without alignment, resistivity is one or two orders of magnitude higher in the through-thickness direction than in either in-plane direction, and the resistivity is lowest along the fiber direction. This behavior is believed to be due to the in-plane direction of resin flow during processing, which preferentially aligns elongated particles such as CNTs in the lamination plane, particularly along the fiber direction where the composite permeability is expected to be highest [12]. References [5,6] also reported higher through-thickness resistivities compared to in-plane before alignment, although those investigations had bi-directionally oriented glass fibers in the lamination plane rather than unidirectional as in the present investigation. The $V_f = 55\%$ composite has higher resistivity in all directions versus the $V_f = 45\%$ composite when no alignment field was applied, which may be attributed to the lower matrix content and consequently smaller number of CNTs in the $V_f = 55\%$ composite per unit volume.

Figure 3: Models with boundary conditions for composite in direct contact with electrodes. Voltage and distance are non-dimensional.

Figure 4: Models with boundary conditions for composite separated from electrodes with PTFE release film. Voltage and distance are non-dimensional.

Figure 5: DC resistivity of cured composites.

With alignment, the resistivity of $V_f = 45\%$ composites through the thickness (i.e., along the alignment direction) decreased by a factor of 4 to 8, which is considered only borderline significant based on scatter that can be expected due to variations specimen preparation and electrical measurements [13]. In comparison, the resistivity of $V_f = 55\%$ composites through the thickness decreased by a factor of 12 to 43 with alignment, which is considered significant. Reduced alignment in the $V_f = 45\%$ composites can be attributed to the material's lower initial resistivity through the thickness, which reduces the polarizability of the CNTs in a fixed magnitude alignment field [8,14]. Improved electrical tailoring can be expected if a lower concentration of CNTs is used in the $V_f = 45\%$ composite. The longitudinal and in-plane transverse resistivities of the composites were about the same or slightly elevated in the $V_f = 45\%$ composite at both frequencies and in the $V_f = 55\%$ composite at the 100 Hz frequency. Therefore, the 100 Hz frequency performs slightly better than the 1,000 Hz frequency across all cases investigated.

Overall, the magnitude of initial electrical anisotropy was reduced by the application of electrical field during cure. Without alignment, the material's resistivity through the thickness was roughly 10 to 100 times higher than the in-plane resistivities, whereas with alignment, the ratio decreased to slightly less than 1 in the best case (i.e., 100 Hz alignment field, $V_f = 45\%$). This result is marginally better than the ratio of about 4 obtained by Domingues et al. [6]. For comparison purposes, results from a similar investigation with round-shaped conductive nanofiller (carbon black) in GFRP composites [13] may be instructive: (a) the lowest values of through-thickness resistivity after alignment were of the same order of magnitude as the in-plane resistivities (roughly 10^8 to 10^9 $\Omega\text{-cm}$ — or roughly 1-2 orders of magnitude less than the current results); (b) lower filler contents (e.g., 0.3 wt% and 0.5 wt%) were markedly better than higher contents (e.g., 1 wt% and 1.5 wt%) for alignment; (c) electric fields of about 1,000 V/cm provided the best alignment; and (d) 100 Hz was the best frequency for alignment. Despite the appearance of using ideal material and process parameters in the current investigation based on the findings of Ref. [13] involving carbon black, it is possible that the high aspect ratio of CNTs requires different optimal parameters. Further investigation is required to determine such optimal parameters.

5 FINITE ELEMENT RESULTS

Figure 6 shows the electric field distributions in the uncured composites with no release film. The arrows show the direction of electric field lines in between the electrodes. The electric field lines are not uniformly oriented everywhere in the resin. Since the CNTs align in the direction of electric field lines, it can be expected that the CNTs will not be uniformly oriented, as well. Additionally, it is observed that the magnitude (shown by the colored contours) of electric field is not uniform in the matrix, particularly in the $V_f = 50\%$ composite. A large variation in electric field strength is observed near closely-spaced fibers.

Figure 6: Spatial distribution of electric field norm (V/cm) for uncured composite in direct contact with electrodes. Arrows indicate direction of electric field.

Due to the non-uniform electric field strength, the suspended CNTs experience dielectrophoretic forces. A polarized CNT experiences a force in the direction of the gradient of the magnitude of electric field squared [8,14]. The arrows in Fig. 7 show the direction of the gradient of electric field square. Given the spatial variation in the direction of the arrows, it can be expected that the CNTs will be displaced from their initial positions. For example, based on the directions of the arrows in Fig. 7, one would expect the CNTs to be driven out of the boxed regions shown in between two adjacent glass fibers that are lined up with the global field direction (i.e. horizontally). Such a displacement of CNTs could locally increase the resistivity in the transverse in-plane direction (vertical, in these figures) more than through-thickness (horizontal) direction. Most regions between fibers with other relative positions do not show this feature, however. It should also be kept in mind that the analysis assumes an initially uniform distribution of CNTs throughout the matrix, which may not be realistic due to resin flow during processing.

A trend similar to the case of electrodes touching the uncured composite is observed with respect to electric field lines and the direction of gradient of electric field square when using a PTFE release film (Figs. 8, 9). Importantly, it is seen that the strength of the electric field in the resin decreases when using PTFE release film, due to the low dielectric constant of the film. Figure 10 compares the electric field strength along the line A-A shown in Figs. 6a and 8a for the $V_f = 40\%$ composites without and with release film. The electric field strength is non-uniform along line A-A and is much higher within the release film as compared to the resin. The electrical quantity that remains constant across the film/resin interface is the displacement current, given by the product of dielectric constant and the electric field. To maintain a constant displacement current across the interface, the electric field in the film (dielectric constant = 2) is high in comparison to the resin (dielectric constant = 100).

Figure 7: Direction of gradient of electric field square for uncured composite in direct contact with electrodes. The large arrows highlight the direction of dielectrophoretic forces acting on CNTs in certain regions between glass fibers.

Figure 8: Spatial distribution of electric field norm (V/cm) for PTFE film between uncured composite and electrodes. Arrows indicate direction of electric field.

Figure 9: Direction of gradient of electric field square for PTFE film between uncured composite and electrodes.

Figure 10: Electric field strength for uncured composite with $V_f = 40\%$. Electric field magnitude plotted along Line A-A in Figs. 6a and 8a.

6 CONCLUSION

Tailoring of the directional DC electrical resistivity of unidirectionally reinforced GFRP composites containing 0.5 wt% MWCNTs in the matrix was investigated by electrically aligning the CNTs during gelation using AC electric fields of 1,000 V/cm strength and frequencies of 100 and 1,000 Hz. The alignment field was applied through the thickness with the aim of minimizing the through-thickness resistivity. Without CNT alignment, composites having glass fiber volume contents of 45% and 55% had through-thickness resistivities one and two orders of magnitude higher, respectively, in comparison to the in-plane directions, and lowest resistivity parallel to the fibers. Greater reductions in through-thickness resistivity were obtained with the $V_f = 55\%$ composite than the $V_f = 45\%$ composite, although in neither case could the in-plane resistivities be significantly increased with CNT alignment. Thus, under the best alignment conditions, through-thickness resistivities were roughly of the same order of magnitude as the in-plane resistivities. The 100 Hz alignment frequency was slightly better than 1,000 Hz for tailoring resistivity for both glass fiber volume contents. These experimental results are

considered preliminary, and further investigation of CNT concentrations and electric field parameters is recommended to determine optimal alignment conditions.

Numerical analysis showed that the presence of continuous glass fibers creates a highly non-uniform electric field in the liquid epoxy upon application of the AC alignment field. Since the electric field lines go around the glass fibers, CNT chains forming in response to the field are not expected to be perfectly aligned through the thickness. The variation in electric field increases with increasing glass fiber volume content in the composite. A stronger alignment field is obtained in the GFRP composite when the alignment electrodes are in direct contact with the composite, in comparison to electrodes separated from the composite by a release film of low dielectric constant. If a release film is required to process the composite, it is suggested to use one of high dielectric constant and/or very low thickness (e.g. a release coat rather than a separate film).

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

This material is based upon work supported by the U.S. Army Research Office under Grant No. W911NF-07-1-0395.

REFERENCES

- [1] Z. Ounaies, C. Park, K. E. Wise, E. J. Siochi, and J. S. Harrison, Electrical properties of single wall carbon nanotube reinforced polyimide composites, *Composites Science and Technology*, **63**, 2003, pp. 1637-1646 ([doi: 10.1016/S0266-3538\(03\)00067-8](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0266-3538(03)00067-8)).
- [2] T. Tallman, F. Semperlotti, and K. W. Wang, Enhanced health monitoring of fibrous composites with aligned carbon nano-tube networks and electrical impedance tomography, *Proc. Health Monitoring of Structural and Biological Systems 2012 (Ed. T. Kundu)*, SPIE Vol. 8348, Bellingham, WA, USA, 2012, Paper 83480G-1 ([doi: 10.1117/12.914461](https://doi.org/10.1117/12.914461)).
- [3] T. N. Tallman, S. Gungor, K. W. Wang, and C. E. Bakis, Damage detection via electrical impedance tomography in glass fiber/epoxy laminates with carbon black filler, *Structural Health Monitoring*, **14**, 2015, pp. 100-109 ([doi: 10.1177/1475921714554142](https://doi.org/10.1177/1475921714554142)).
- [4] S. Gungor and C. E. Bakis, Indentation damage detection in glass/epoxy composite laminates with electrically tailored conductive nanofiller, *J. Intelligent Material Systems and Structures*, published online before print, 2015, pp. 1-10 ([doi: 10.1177/1045389X15577644](https://doi.org/10.1177/1045389X15577644)).
- [5] M. H. G. Wichmann, J. Sumfleth, F. H. Gojny, M. Quaresimin, B. Fiedler, and K. Schulte, Glass-fibre-reinforced composites with enhanced mechanical and electrical properties - Benefits and limitations of a nanoparticle modified matrix, *Engineering Fracture Mechanics*, **73**, 2006, pp. 2346-2359 ([doi: 10.1016/j.engfracmech.2006.05.015](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.engfracmech.2006.05.015)).
- [6] D. Domingues, E. Logakis, and A. A. Skordos, The use of an electric field in the preparation of glass fibre/epoxy composites containing carbon nanotubes, *Carbon*, **50**, 2012, pp. 2493-2503 ([doi: 10.1016/j.carbon.2012.01.072](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.carbon.2012.01.072)).
- [7] A. Sharma, C. E. Bakis, and K. W. Wang, Tailored alignment of functionalized multiwall carbon nanotubes in epoxy, *Proc. 2008 Fall Technical Conference*, Society for the Advancement of Materials and Process Engineering, Covina, CA, USA, 2008, Paper No. 41, 11 p.
- [8] A. Sharma, C. E. Bakis, and K. W. Wang, Effect of electrostatic and electro-hydrodynamic forces on the chaining of carbon nanofibers in liquid epoxy," *J. Physics D: Applied Physics*, **43**, 2010, Paper 175402, 10 p. ([doi: 10.1088/0022-3727/43/17/175402](https://doi.org/10.1088/0022-3727/43/17/175402)).
- [9] S. Y. Fu and B. Lauke, The elastic modulus of misaligned short-fiber-reinforced polymers, *Composite Science and Technology*, **58**, 1998, pp. 389-400.
- [10] S. L. Shi, L. Z. Zhang, and J. S. Li, Electrical and dielectric properties of multiwall carbon nanotube/polyaniline composites, *J. Polymer Research*, **16**, 2009, pp. 395-399.
- [11] COMSOL, Inc. Burlington, MA, USA.
- [12] J. van der Westhuizen and J. P. Du Plessis, Quantification of unidirectional fiber bed permeability, *J. Composite Materials*, **28**, 1994, pp. 619-637.

- [13] S. Gungor and C. E. Bakis, Anisotropic networking of carbon black in glass/epoxy composites using electric field, *J. Composite Materials*, **49**, 2015, pp. 535-544 ([doi: 10.1177/0021998314521256](https://doi.org/10.1177/0021998314521256)).
- [14] M. Dimaki and P. Bøggild, Dielectrophoresis of carbon nanotubes using microelectrodes: a numerical study, *Nanotechnology*, **15**, 2004, pp. 1095-1102 ([doi: 10.1088/0957-4484/15/8/039](https://doi.org/10.1088/0957-4484/15/8/039)).